

THE ROLE OF RESORT AREAS IN THE SYSTEM OF PROTECTED NATURAL AREAS

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Annotation. This article analyzes the ecological and social significance of resort zones within the system of protected natural areas. Resort zones are specially protected territories that not only provide opportunities for rehabilitation, treatment, and recreation, but also serve to preserve unique natural resources. They play a key role in maintaining biodiversity, protecting natural landscapes, and ensuring ecological sustainability. The article examines the legal status of resort zones based on the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Resorts” and “On Protected Natural Areas,” as well as the ecological restrictions, control mechanisms, and management systems applicable to them. Furthermore, it emphasizes the importance of sustainable tourism, the development of health infrastructure, and the preservation of ecological balance in the development of these zones.

Keywords. Resort zone, natural resource, treatment, recreation, social protection, biodiversity.

Nature protection and rational use are one of the main directions of state policy, in this regard, the system of protected natural areas is of great importance. And resort natural areas play an important role in this system. Because they are not only important for maintaining the health of the population, but also for the development of regional and global tourism, employment generation, and economic development. Over the past 50 years, human activity has changed ecosystems faster and more extensively than in any comparable period in our history, more than 60% of the world's ecosystems have already been destroyed. These changes have led to many economic gains, but there are also growing environmental costs - loss of biodiversity, public health, climate change, land degradation, water scarcity - which lead to many economic, social and cultural losses. At the same time, long-term investments by national governments in protected areas systems are being observed globally to be effective in preventing negative consequences and bringing significant economic benefits. In this direction, resort natural areas are an effective tool to reverse biodiversity loss, protect citizens from the impacts of climate change, and preserve entire ecosystems that are important for everyone.

Resorts are ecologically, socially and economically integrated territories intended for the treatment, rehabilitation and recreation of the population.

The basis of the activity of resorts is the natural healing resources of the territory in which they are located, since it is the condition of these resources that determines the effectiveness of recreational (i.e. recreation and rehabilitation) and therapeutic activities. The main role in ensuring the quality of natural healing resources and the ecological condition of resorts lies in the legal system, i.e. the protective legal order. However, in recent years, significant changes have occurred in the legislation on resorts, and the negative consequences of these changes are not long in coming.

Resort areas are places with natural healing resources used to restore and strengthen human health, which are specially protected by the state. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Nature Protection", the Law "On Protected Natural Areas" and other regulatory legal acts establish the status of resort areas and the procedure for their use. On the basis of these legal acts, resort areas are included in the protected natural areas.

Protected natural areas provide for the protection of all natural objects located within their borders. The main difference between a resort natural area and other categories of protected natural areas is that the purpose of their creation is twofold and does not coincide with the purpose of creating protected natural areas of other categories. On the one hand, resorts are created to use natural resources for medicinal purposes, on the other hand, they should ensure the use of natural medicinal resources in a way that allows such activities to be carried out with minimal harm to the environment and natural objects and resources, that is, to harmonize the use of natural resources and objects and their protection.

According to Article 36 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 710-II dated 03.12.2004 "On Protected Natural Areas", a resort is defined as a protected natural area with healing and health-improving properties, mineral springs, healing mud layers, favorable climate and other conditions. Legal regulation of the use and protection of resorts is carried out on the basis of Chapter IX of the Land Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This chapter is devoted to the lands of protected natural areas and objects. In addition, Article 73 of the Land Code directly determines the legal regime of health-improving areas - resort lands and lands within these territories.

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